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**ANALYSIS OF THE STATUTE
AND THE FIRST YEAR OF THE ACTIVITIES
OF LVIV SOCIETY OF GALICIAN PHYSICIANS
(«TOWARZYSTWO LEKARZÓW
GALICYJSKICH»)**

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Ключевые слова: *медицина, профсоюз, общество, врачи, защита*

Abstract. *Analysis of the statute and the first year of the activities of Lviv Society of Galician Physicians («Towarzystwo lekarzów Galicyjskich»). Berest I.R., Berest R.Ya., Pasichnyk M.S., Savchuk H.M., Oliynyk M.A. Based on the principle of historicism, system analysis, structural functionalism, dialectics and synergetics, the paper analyzes the statute and activity of the Lviv Society of Galician Physicians, the first trade union organization in the medicine. The state of affairs as well as development of historiography of the issue including the history of the medical and trade union movement, the names of the Society founders is shown. There was proved that the overall problems of all population segments became the main event among physicians of the second half of the nineteenth century. This organization played a prominent role in the development of medicine in Galicia. The activity of the Society was regulated by the statute. Each member when joining the Society, pledged to comply with all the provisions of the statute and had to care for its growth and the glory. Active members had to be present at scientific meetings and provide observations on the state of the medical affair, that is, to provide statistics on the diseases and patients they have been treated, as well as to share the experience gained in practice. The purpose of the organization and its activities were primarily socio-economic and cultural-educational ones. Under its control, the Society kept a record of the movement of patients in Lviv hospitals (kept statistics of all cured patients), analyzed new methods in the treatment of fever, various pathologies and other issues. The members of the Society promised to meet every first Saturday of the month to participate in scientific meetings. They discussed major events in the life of the organization, read correspondence and planned work for the next month. Once a year, in December, the Society of Galician physicians held an annual meeting, which provided a full annual financial report, discussed the issues of new members and those who left the organization, announced the names of new honorary and advisory members.*

Реферат. *Анализ устава и первого года деятельности Львовского Общества галицких врачей («Towarzystwo lekarzów galicyjskich»). Берест И.Р., Берест Р.Я., Пасечник М.С., Савчук Г.Н., Олейник Н.А. На основе принципа историзма, системного анализа, структурного функционализма, диалектики и синергетики в статье проанализирован устав и показано начало деятельности Львовского Общества галицийских врачей – первой профсоюзной организации медицинской сферы. Показано современное состояние и развитие историографии проблематики, исследована история медицинского и профсоюзного движения, названы фамилии и имена основателей Общества. Доказано, что главным событием в среде врачей второй половины XIX в. стали общие проблемы для всех слоев населения, в результате чего было основано новое движение по материальной и моральной защите и собственных работников. Эта организация сыграла заметную роль в становлении медицины Галичины. Деятельность Общества регламентировал устав. Каждый из членов, вступая в Общество, принимал на себя обязанность соблюдения всех положений устава и должен был заботиться о росте и славе организации. Действующие члены должны были обязательно присутствовать на научных заседаниях и предоставлять наблюдения относительно состояния лечебного дела. То есть предоставлять статистические данные относительно болезней и больных, которых они лечили, а также делиться опытом, полученным на практике. Целью создания и деятельности организации были прежде всего социально-экономические и культурно-образовательные цели. Под своим контролем Общество держало учет движения больных в львовских госпиталях (вела статистику всех вылеченных пациентов), анализировало новые методы в лечении лихорадки, различных патологий и другие вопросы. Члены Общества обязывались*

собирались каждую первую субботу месяца для участия в научных заседаниях. На них обсуждались основные события из жизни организации, зачитывалась корреспонденция и планировалась работа на следующий месяц. Один раз в год, в декабре, Общество галицких врачей проводило годовые собрания, где предоставлялся полный финансовый отчет годовой деятельности, обсуждались вопросы о новых членах и тех, которые покинули организацию, объявлялись имена новых почетных и советательных членов.

In modern conditions, when determining the ways of further development of Ukraine and medical science in particular, the growth of scientific interest in own history, rethinking of historical facts, ideological distortions, hidden events and phenomena is obvious. We are always interested in: where it all began? What preceded this or that event? It is clear that medical science appeared a long time ago, but organizations that aimed to protect medical workers is a new topic.

Therefore, the activity of the first medical societies in the Ukrainian lands, the problem of their formation as organizations aimed at protecting economic and social interests of medical workers, taking care of their cultural, educational, health and other needs was no exception. Such societies have become prototypes of modern trade unions.

The analysis of domestic literature on the study of the history of medicine and its trade unions shows the need for a new, comprehensive study, connected, firstly, with a relatively little number of processed

sources of information. Secondly, this topic is diverse and multifaceted and many of its aspects need a deeper and more thorough review. Thirdly, this problematics provides substantial material for the scientific study of other key issues of the complex history of Galicia in the Austrian period, in particular: the organization of health care, medical education, governance system, economic and social development, the rise of Ukrainian national movement, etc. Fourthly, in the conditions of building democratic institutions of independent Ukraine, the analysis and accumulation of historical experience has not only scientific, but also cognitive, ideological-political and especially applied, practical significance.

In the XIX century trade unions occupied a special place in the life of Galician society. We now know of more than 30 professional organizations in Eastern Galicia that had their own publications, large united groups, often dealing with difficult social issues.

Last page of statute of Society of Galician Physicians, 1877

There is no information in the Ukrainian scientific literature about the professional societies of physicians in Galicia, which is due to a certain gap in the study of the history of medicine. Although we have information about the study of societies and organizations in other areas [1, 2, 4, 5]. Therefore, the study is based on Polish historiography, in particular the works of J. Grek, V. Zimbitysky, M. Herman, V. Novitsky [7, 8, 10]. Our scientific intelligence was based on sources such as the society's statutes, dated 1867 and 1877, the general report on the creation of the organization, the

Chronicle of Activities for 50 years, financial documents (annual reports) and the press of that time.

Recent scientific research shows that the democratization of Galician society was significantly influenced by the revolution of 1848, reforms, decrees and resolutions of the Austro-Hungarian government. A special place among them was occupied by the imperial patent of December 20, 1859, which regulated the conditions and principles of creating professional associations [3, p. 68-71, 176].

Title page of "Gazeta Likarska"

In our study we **set a goal**: to study the situation in medicine of Eastern Galicia in the second half of the XIX century, based on new, still unknown sources, to show the process of creation, to note the role of the founders of the Galician Society, and to analyze the organization. On the basis of the main document of the society to consider its structure, responsibilities of members and to determine the results of the first year of activity of the organization

which became the predecessor of creation of medical self-government.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

To solve the tasks, we used a number of methods, including historical and medical. Thanks to the latter it was possible to reconstruct the events and facts in time space, which made it possible to recreate the process of development of the Society of Galician Physicians, its history with all its features. The

system approach provided a study of the interaction of the medical trade union and civil society as subsystems of the general social system. The biblionic method made it possible to find out the state of study of the researched problem and the ways of its solution through the analysis of the statute, annual reports and reports of the management of the society. In general, the methodological basis of the work is the principles of historicism, systematic, structural analysis, objectivity, comprehensiveness and continuity in the consideration of the chosen topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the beginning of 1867, Lviv physicians recognized the need to create their own professional

association to organize social protection, to create a fund to support the sick, infirm and impoverished colleagues, as well as widows and orphans. Thus, it was decided to establish a separate Medical Society [7, p. 3].

In general, work on the organization's statute lasted from February 12, 1867 to the end of May of that year [9, p. 64]. On the 8th of September, 1867 municipal council of Galician vicegerency granted authorization for the establishment of the Society of Galician Physicians and under № L. 15.327/834 approved its statute, which numbered 89 sections [14, p. 11].

Title page of statute of Society of Galician Physicians, 1867

After concluding the statute, which was prepared on the model of the Warsaw Medical Society, the executive committee invited all local doctors to discuss and improve the statutory provisions, as well as their adaptation to local health problems [12, p. 5].

The initiators of the establishing of the Professional Medical Society and the authors of the statute were local doctors: Boleslaw Głowacki, Józef Miller, August Noskiewicz and Zygmunt Rieger.

After that, the executive committee convened local physicians and through public journals informed non-residents about the convening of a general meeting of doctors in Lviv to hold elections of leaders [8, p. 6].

In accordance with the provisions of the statute, the purpose of the Society of Galician Physicians was to work together on the development of medicine, primarily in the direction of its practical application, taking into account the relations of the

population of the state as a whole; promoting a spirit of cohesion and friendship between health professionals in order to jointly oversee medical affairs; providing financial assistance to impoverished colleagues, families of deceased colleagues (widows and orphans).

After discussions the organization was renamed the "Society of Galician Physicians based in Lviv" and housed in a building on Kokhanovsky street (now Konopnytska Str., 3 – authors).

On December 2, 1867, the founding meeting of the Society took place in the large conference hall of the Lviv City Hall. 47 practitioners of Lviv came to the meeting. The feast speech was put in charge of Dr. Sh. Matsiyovsky, who thanked everyone for their presence and wished fruitful work [12, p. 6].

Immediately during the constituent assembly, the Board of the Society was elected. Its chairman was

Dr. Szczesny Matsiyowski, the deputy - Dr. Karol Berthlef, the treasurer – Dr. Franciszek Kosinski, the deputy treasurer – Dr. Wojciech Wolek, the secretaries were Dr. Zygmunt Rieger and Dr. Oscar Widman.

Dr. Bolesław Głowacki, Dr. Józef Molendzinski, Dr. August Noskiewicz, Dr. Herman Witz, Dr. Grzegorz Zimbitski and Dr. Józef Finger were elected members of the Administrative Board. The latter immediately resigned, so Dr. Boguslaw Longchamps was elected in his stead [7, p. 4-5].

The society consisted of active, honorary and advisory members. The number of members was not limited in number. Any physician of Galicia with academic degree obtained or confirmed by the Austrian authorities could be its active member.

Annual report of the "Society of Galician Physicians" for 1868

As a consequence of celebration of scientific merits, the Society afforded an opportunity to physicians, domestic scientists or those from abroad to be the honorary members.

Not only physicians but other citizens who replenished its funds with one-time or annual donations to the Society's treasury were the advisory members. Later, after ten years of existence, after a

long debate on improving the work and expanding the Society, another category of members appeared in the statute – corresponding ones. The physicians outside Galicia, whose actions benefited the Society could be the ones [15, p. 3].

Each member, joining the Society, pledged to comply with all the provisions of the statute and had to take care of the growth and glory of the organization. Active members had to be present at scientific meetings and provide observations on the state of medical affairs, that is, to provide statistics on diseases and patients they have treated, as well as to share experiences gained in practice. Each of the active members or those who joined the Society had to pay an entrance fee of 10 florins. In addition to this payment, annually he pledged to pay half a percent point of the income from his medical practice to the Society's fund. The amount of this annual payment was to be not less than 5 fl., maximal amount was not limited. Advisory members made a one-time significant donation that was individual to each member. Honorary members had no obligations to pay [8, p. 372].

Money received from donations was primarily used to support widows, orphans and impoverished doctors [14, p. 2].

From among the active members of the Society permanently residing in Lviv, a board of administration, a chairman of the Society, a vice-chairman, two secretaries, a treasurer and a deputy treasurer were elected for a term of one year. The board of administration consisted of a chairman or vice-chairman, six active members, two secretaries, a treasurer and a deputy treasurer a total of 11 people.

The members of the Society pledged to meet every first Saturday of the month at 6 p.m. to participate in scientific meetings. They discussed the main events in the life of the organization, read the correspondence and planned work for the next month. Once a year, in December, the Society of Galician Physicians held an annual meeting which provided a full financial report of annual activities, discussed issues concerning new members and those who left the organization, announced the names of new honorary and advisory members. At the annual meeting, the board of administration and other employees were elected by secret ballot.

The Board of the Society pledged to publish the "Yearbook of the Society of Galician Physicians", which was considered a publication and contained official information on the financial statements of the organization, the results of scientific meetings, extracts from the latest medical newspapers and magazines, statistics and meteorological data, interesting clinical cases, bibliographic extracts from the

latest medical publications. At the annual meeting it was also possible to make changes to the statute, put them to the vote and in case of approval to start to work on [11, p. 64].

All donations and incomes of the Society were divided into three unequal parts: the fund of administrative expenses, reserved or fixed fund or auxiliary (pension) fund. The administrative fund accounted for 1/3 of the income from the annual and entrance fees of active members. The fixed fund included all contributions of advisory members, as well as gifts, donations of more than 50 fl., 1/3 of income from annual and entrance fees of active members, net revenue of "Yearbook" and other printed materials of the Society. The auxiliary fund included all contributions of advisory members, as well as gifts, donations of less than 50 fl., 1/3 of the income from annual and entrance fees of active members, bank interest and all savings from the administrative fund. Representatives of the board reported on all revenues every three months at the meetings of the administrative council. Only impoverished widows and orphans could count on financial assistance. [14, p. 9].

As of the end of 1868, the number of active members was 98, of whom 59 were from Lviv and 39 lived outside the city. To understand the sphere of influence and representation of the Society, we will give the names of the cities of the region where the active members were represented – Buchach, Brody, Tarnów, Bochnia, Vienna, Zolochiv, Wadowice, Krakow, Dolya, Lancut, Rava-Ruska, Stryi, Lisky, Ropchysia, Rzeszow, Drohobych, Husiatyn, Yaroslavl, Kamianka, Terebovlia, Novyi Sanch, Sambir, Chortkiv, Pere-myshlyany, Sniatyn, Nisko, Bibrka, and Turka. Some cities had several representatives [6, p. 14-15].

During the first year of its existence, the Society suffered a heavy loss – the active member Dr. Boguslaw Kobuzovsky died. In total, in 1868 there were ten scientific meetings, at which the average attendance was 28 members, and 11 meetings of the administrative council, where the issue of financing the construction of the premises of the Society was resolved [12, p. 8-9].

The income of the Society over the year made up 1,595.83 fl. Of these, 1,470 fl. – the contributions of 93 active members, 65 fl. – additional donations of 11 members, 60 fl. 83 c. – income from mortgage letters and savings books. Expenditures totaled 232.91 fl.: printing and lithography, postage and stamps, fee for lighting the meeting room, clerk's services, room maintenance, library needs, etc. The rest of the money remained from the income was invested in mortgage letters of the Credit Society – * 1,172.16 fl. and at interest in the City Savings Bank – 190.76 fl. [16, p. 15-16].

nauki, tam oczywiście jest daleko trudniej wyjść z tej chwilowej ospałości.

Jednak jest to początek; miejmy nadzieję że z tych ogromnych materiałów, które tutejsze szpitale dostarczają, będzie można w przyszłości lepiej korzystać, że ta otępiłość pewnej liczby członków i niechęć przeminie, że coraz większa będzie zachęta do pracy, a wtedy i nasze Towarzystwo będzie mogło obfitsze plony przedłożyć publiczności lekarskiej. Nakoniec zwracamy się do kolegów zamieszkałych na prowincyi, aby nas zechcieli swojemi sprawozdaniami i uwagami wspomagać, jakiejbykolwiek one tyczyły gałęzi sztuki lekarskiej, tym sposobem rozwinię się i ustali większa spójność naukowa członków miejscowych z zamiejscowymi.

Na tych kilku uwagach zakończamy krótki rys zawiązania się i czynności Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich w r. 1868; umieszczone zresztą poniżej protokoły posiedzeń zawierają szczegółowo czynności Towarzystwa.

Członkowie czynni miejscowi Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich.

1. Dr. Armatys Hipolit.
2. „ Berthleff Karol.
3. „ Beiser Mojżesz.
4. „ Chądzyński Jan.
5. „ Czerkawski Julian.
6. „ Festenburg Edward.
7. „ Finger Józef.
8. „ Gębarzewski Ludwik.
9. „ Geistlener Jan.
10. „ Głowacki Bolesław.
11. „ Gross Karol.

12. Dr. Hawranek Ignacy.
13. „ Jasiński Władysław.
14. „ Kosiński Franciszek.
15. „ Kaczkowski Antoni.
16. „ Kierkorowicz Grzegorz.
17. „ Krzczunowicz Piotr.
18. „ Kartsch Maksymilian.
19. „ Kluczenko Bazyli.
20. „ Longchamps Bogusław.
21. „ Łopacki Ludwik.
22. „ Maciejowski Szczesny.
23. „ Molendziński Józef.
24. „ Mosing Bogumił.
25. „ Mosing Kazimierz.
26. „ Moszczański Karol.
27. „ Milleret Józef.
28. „ Nowiński Seweryn.
29. „ Noskiewicz August.
30. „ Nagel Karol.
31. „ Neuhauser Franciszek.
32. „ Orzechowicz Jędrzej.
33. „ Opolski Wiktor.
34. „ Ressig Ignacy.
35. „ Rappaport Maurycy.
36. „ Rektorzik Emil.
37. „ Rieger Zygmunt.
38. „ Reiss Karol.
39. „ Reizes Dawid.
40. „ Rosner Ignacy.
41. „ Schuller Hugo.
42. „ Serda Franciszek.
43. „ Spausta Damian.
44. „ Skałkowski Władysław.
45. „ Stupnicki Juliusz.
46. „ Silberstein Leopold.
47. Mag. Chir. Strasky Wincenty.
48. Dr. Tomanek Józef.

Name list of members of Society of Galician Physicians as of the end of 1867

Another key point of the statute was the maintenance and functioning of the library. At the end of 1868, the Society's book depository numbered more than 200 medical dossiers. Dr. Bogumil Mosing, a physicist in Lviv, donated 178 dossiers in 225 volumes and a large number of medical journals, and Archbishop of the Lviv Armenian Community Hryhoriy Shimonovych gifted 9 of the latest dossiers on botany and zoology. Lviv bookseller Karol Wild presented the Society with several new and old medical dossiers. Dr. Michał Zelenowski sent books about health resort treatment.

Dr. Vladyslav Yasinsky presented two of his own books: "On Water Treatment" and "Critique of Homeopathy", published in Lviv in 1865. Dr. Józef Molendzinski donated to the library his work "On Body Injuries", published in Warsaw in 1867, Dr. Tadeusz Zhulinsky from Paris sent his work "The Brain of Great Russia", published in 1867, and immediately sent the yearbook of the Paris Society of Physicians. The editorial board of the Warsaw "Gazeta Lekarska" sent all issues of the magazine free of charge from the moment of the Society's foundation [16, p. 17-16].

W y k a z
majątku Towarzystwa lekarzy galicyjskich z końcem
roku 1868.

A. Dochody.

	złr.	kr.	złr.	kr.
1. Członkowie Towarzystwa w liczbie 93 złożyli w zwykłych wkładkach .	1.470	.		
2. Członkowie Towarzystwa w liczbie 11 złożyli przez powiększone wkładki .	65	.		
3. Do tych kwot dolicza się prowizya od listów zastawnych i książeczki kasy oszczędności	60	83		
Razem	1.595	83	1.595	83

N. B. Do dochodów nie jest policzoną zaległość od trzech członków w kwocie 15 złr.

Annual income of Society of Galician Physicians

The debut year of the active work of the Society of Galician Physicians ended with the general annual meeting, which took place on December 19, 1868. Dr. Matsiyovsky chaired it, and 37 active members were present. The agenda included a number of issues, including: determination of honorary members, summing up the year, establishing voting rules [13, p. 29].

CONCLUSIONS

1. On the basis of specific historical sources, the article analyzes the scientific problem, which was to study the creation and first steps of the Society of Galician Physicians - the first organization of medical self-government of Ukraine. This organization played a significant role in the formation of medicine in Galicia. The activities of the Society were regulated by the statute. The purpose of the creation and operation of the organization were primarily socio-economic and cultural-educational goals. The statute was approved by the relevant state

authorities. In general, the Society kept under its control the movement of patients in Lviv hospitals (statistics of all treated patients was kept), new methods in the treatment of fever, various pathologies and other issues were analyzed. Another feature of the Society of Galician physicians was the system of accumulation in a special fund of savings in case of illness or death. There was no such practice in the health care of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy at that time.

2. Drawing parallels with modernity, we can notice that in the middle of the XIX century on the territory of modern Ukraine the principles of medical self-government have already been formed and the basis of health insurance has been laid. In today's reality, we are only striving for this kind of thing in order to get real protection of our rights. Therefore, it makes sense to review the history and improve the experience already gained.

REFERENCES

1. Berest I. [Analysis of Lviv professional press of polygraphists by the example of journals "Czcionka" and "Przewodnik dla spraw drukarsko-litograficznych"]. *Grani*. 2017;20(11):17-21. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1717142>
2. Berest I. [Activity of the «Company of mutual aid of private customers» of Galicia in 1848]. *Naukovi zapysky Nacionalnogo universytetu «Ostrozka akademiia*. Serii «Istorychni nauky». 2018;27:51-56. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.25264/2409-6806-2018-27-51-56>
3. Berest I. [History of trade unions of Ukraine (Eastern Galicia 1817-1918)]. Lviv: Levada; 2017. P. 768. Ukrainian.
4. Berest I. [Lviv general professional association of mutual assistance of printers in 1856-1867. Analysis of activity]. *Grani*. 2018;21(11):6-13. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1718146>
5. Berest I. [Strike struggle with the participation of trade unions in Eastern Galicia]. *Grani*. 2017;20(10):115-20. Ukrainian. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1717140>
6. [Active members outside the Society of Galician Doctors]. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. 1869:14-15. Polish.
7. Grek J, Ziembicki W. [Half a century at a glance at the chronicle of the Lviv medical society (1877-1927)]. 1928:26. Polish.

8. Herman M. From the chronicle of the Lviv Medical Society because of its 30-year anniversary]. *Lwowski Tygodnik Lekarski*. 1908;1:6-14. Polish.
9. [Targeted Galician Medical Society in Lviv]. *Przegląd Lekarski*. 1867;23(8):64. Polish.
10. Nowicki W. [From the history of Lviv Medical Weekly and his successor, the organs of the Lviv Medical Society. (Because of the 50th anniversary of the Society)]. *Polska Gazeta Lekarska*. 1928;20-24:372. Polish.
11. [From the editor «Pamiętnika Tow. Lekarskiego»]. *Przegląd Lekarski*. 1867;23(8):64. Polish.
12. [General report on the establishment and activities of the Society of Galician Doctors in 1868]. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. 1869:5-12. Polish.
13. [The first general annual meeting of the Society of Galician Physicians December 19, 1868]. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. 1869:29-30. Polish.
14. [Draft Act of the Society of Galician Doctors]. *Lwów*. 1867;11. Polish.
15. [Act of the Society of Galician Doctors]. *Lwów*. 1877;16. Polish.
16. [List of assets of the Society of Galician Doctors at the end of 1868]. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. 1869:15-18. Polish.

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Берест І. Р. Аналіз львівської профспілкової преси поліграфістів на прикладі часописів “Czcionka” і “Przewodnik dla spraw drukarsko-litograficznych”. *Грані*. 2017. Т. 20, № 11. С. 17-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1717142>
2. Берест І. Діяльність «Товариства взаємної допомоги приватних службовців» Галичини в 1848 році: Наукові записки Нац. університету «Острозька академія». Серія «Історичні науки». Острог, 2018. Вип. 27: На пошану Володимира Трофимовича. С. 51-56. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25264/2409-6806-2018-27-51-56>
3. Берест І. Історія професійних спілок України (Східна Галичина 1817 – 1918 pp.). Львів: Левада, 2017. 768 с.
4. Берест І. Р. Загальноміське професійне товариство взаємодопомоги друкарів Львова в 1856-1867 роках. Аналіз діяльності. *Грані*. 2018. Т. 21, № 11. С. 6-13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1718146>
5. Берест І. Р. Страйкова боротьба з участю профспілок у Східній Галичині у другій половині XIX – на початку XX століття. *Грані*. 2017. Т. 20, № 10. С. 115-120. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15421/1717140>
6. Członkowie czynni zamiejscowi Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. Lwów: z c.k. galicyjskiej drukarni rządowej, 1869. S.14-15.
7. Grek J., Ziembicki W. Pół wieku rzut oka na kronikę towarzystwa lekarskiego lwowskiego (1877-1927). *Lwów: z drukarni i litografji Piller-Neumanna*, 1928. 26 s.
8. Herman M. Z. kroniki Towarzystwa Lekarskiego Lwowskiego z powodu 30-letniej rocznicy. *Lwowski Tygodnik Lekarski*. 1908. No. 1. S. 6-14.
9. Namierzone Galicyjskie Towarzystwo lekarskie we Lwowie. *Przegląd Lekarski*. 1867. 23 lut. (No. 8). S. 64.
10. Nowicki W. Z dziejów Lwowskiego Tygodnika Lekarskiego i jego następcy, organów Towarzystwa Lekarskiego Lwowskiego. (z powodu 50-lecia tegoż Towarzystwa). *Polska Gazeta Lekarska*. 1928. No. 20-24. S. 372-446.
11. Od Redakcyi «Pamiętnika Tow. Lekarskiego». *Przegląd Lekarski*. 1867. 23 lut. (No. 8). S. 64.
12. Ogólne sprawozdanie z zawiązania się i czynności Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich w roku 1868. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. Lwów: z c.k. galicyjskiej drukarni rządowej, 1869. S. 5-12.
13. Pierwsze walne doroczne Zgromadzenie Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich 19 Grudnia 1868. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. Lwów: z c.k. galicyjskiej drukarni rządowej, 1869. S. 29-30.
14. Projekt ustawy Towarzystwa lekarzy galicyjskich. *Lwów: z drukarni K.Pillera*, 1867. 11 s.
15. Ustawa Towarzystwa Lekarzy Galicyjskich. *Lwów: nakładem Towarzystwa, z drukarni «Dziennika Polskiego» A. J. O. Rogosza we Lwowie*, 1877. 16 s.
16. Wykaz majątku Towarzystwa lekarzy galicyjskich z końcem roku 1868. *Rocznik Towarzystwa lekarzów galicyjskich za rok 1868*. Lwów: z c.k. galicyjskiej drukarni rządowej, 1869. S. 15-18.

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